

Single-Pixel Imaging in Space and Time with Optically-Modulated Free Electrons

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Single-pixel imaging, originally developed in light optics, facilitates fast three-dimensional sample reconstruction, as well as probing with light wavelengths undetectable by conventional multi-pixel detectors. However, the spatial resolution of optics-based single-pixel microscopy is limited by diffraction to hundreds of nanometers. Here, we propose an implementation of single-pixel imaging relying on attainable modifications of currently available ultrafast electron microscopes in which optically-modulated electrons are used instead of photons to achieve sub-nanometer spatially- and temporally-resolved single-pixel imaging. We simulate electron beam profiles generated by interaction with the optical field produced by an externally programable spatial light modulator and demonstrate the feasibility of the method by showing that the sample image and its temporal evolution can be reconstructed using realistic imperfect illumination patterns. Electron single-pixel imaging holds strong potential for application in low-dose probing of beam-sensitive biological and molecular samples, including rapid screening during in-situ experiments.

Introduction

Single-pixel imaging (SPI) is a key application of structured-wave illumination. This method, which has been recently developed in the context of optical imaging, relies on the interrogation of a certain object using a number of spatially-modulated illumination patterns while synchronously measuring the total intensity of the scattered light captured by a single-pixel detector [1,2,3,4]. Key elements in this method are (1) a spatial light modulator (SLM), which provides the spatial encoding of the illumination patterns that is necessary for image reconstruction, and (2) the inherent ‘sparsity’ of typical real-space images, such that the bulk of the information is only contained in a limited number of pixels, and consequently, compressed sensing can be used [5,6,7].

The idea behind SPI is to perform a number of sequential measurements with specific illumination patterns expressed on a sufficiently complete basis that can be either incoherent (random patterns) or spatially-correlated (such as Hadamard or Fourier bases) with the object to be imaged. The ensemble of M measurements, identified by the vector χ , is then correlated to the image T (sample transmission function) with a number of pixels N_{pix} (in which one usually has $M \ll N_{pix}$) through the $M \times N_{pix}$ measurement matrix H , which contains the employed SLM patterns, such that $\chi = HT$. An image reconstruction algorithm is then used to retrieve a reconstructed image T^* .

The fact that the number of measurements necessary for reconstruction of an image can be substantially smaller than the total number of unknown pixels is an extremely interesting aspect for electron microscopy, since it would entail lower noise, faster response time, and lower radiation dose with respect to conventional imaging approaches. Such advantages would be particularly appealing in the context of electron imaging of nano-objects in their biological and/or chemical natural environment, for which the minimization of the electron dose is critical [8,9] to avoid sample damage. Initial attempts have been made using MeV electrons with beam profiles controlled by laser image projection on a photocathode [10]. This method is, however, incompatible with the sub-nanometer resolution achieved in transmission electron microscopes (TEMs) through electron collimation stages. Sub-nanometer resolution for SPI thus requires patterning of high-quality coherent beams. In TEMs, SPI has never been proposed and adopted before, mainly due to the lack of fast and versatile electron modulators that would be able to generate the required rapidly changing electron patterns.

Here, we propose to implement SPI in a TEM by illuminating the sample using structured electron beams created by a Photonic free-Electron Modulator (here referred as PELM). The PELM is based on properly synthesized localized electromagnetic fields that are able to create an efficient electron modulation for programable time/energy and space/momentum control of electron beams. Our approach adopts optical field patterns to imprint on the phase and amplitude profile of the electron wave function – an externally-controlled well-defined modulation varying both in time and space while the electron pulse crosses the light field. The PELM concept relies on the ability to modulate electrons with optical fields [11,12,13] down to attosecond timescales [14,15,16,17], and in fact, it is an evolution of our recent experimental demonstration of the generation and control of ultrafast vortex electron pulses via chiral plasmonic fields [18]. In essence, we overcome the problem of designing and fabricating complicated electron-optics elements by resorting to shaping light beams, which has been proven a much easier task to perform, while in addition it enables fast temporal modulation. Indeed, a critical advantage of our approach with respect to existing methods lies in the possibility of achieving an unprecedented ultrafast switching and an extreme flexibility of electron manipulation, which can also open new quantum microscopy applications [19, 20].

A suitable platform for generating the required light field configurations is represented by a light-opaque, yet electron-transparent thin film on which an externally-controlled optical pattern is projected from a SLM. The SLM provides an out-of-plane electric field, $E_z(x,y)$, with a customized transverse configuration that embodies the required laterally-changing phase and amplitude profiles. In such a configuration, the spatial pattern imprinted on the incident light field by the SLM is directly transferred onto the transverse profile of the electron wavepacket [21,22]. Different portions of the electron wave profile experience a different phase modulation as dictated by the

optical pattern. We can thus obtain an externally-programable electron beam with a laterally-changing encoded modulation. Moreover, the ability to modulate the electron phase and amplitude has the potential to overcome Poisson noise [23, 24], which is a key aspect that renders the SPI method not only feasible but also advantageous in terms of low-dose imaging.

A synchronized intensity measurement followed by a compressive-sensing reconstruction could then be used to retrieve the sample image. Of course, the possibility to use compressed sensing algorithms strictly relies on the amount of *a priori* information known about the object under investigation [7]. Also, by adopting ultrashort light and electron pulses, one could exploit their temporal resolution to retrieve depth information of the investigated objects (3D imaging). In fact, by correlating the detection time of the electrons after the interaction –i.e., the electron time of flight– with the time of illumination, it would be possible to obtain the spatial distribution of distances travelled by the electron within the sample, as Stellinga *et al.* [25] have recently shown for light-based microscopy. Practically speaking, the measurement of the temporal distribution of a structured electron pulse can be performed using a synchronized TM_{110} microwave cavity acting as a temporal-streaking probe for electrons [26]. Such scheme will be able to provide the full 3D representation of an object without the need of more involved and time-consuming tomographic methods or single-particle analysis algorithms [27,28].

In Fig. 1a-c, we present the different single-pixel schemes that can be implemented in an electron microscope for 2D spatial imaging (Fig. 1a), 1D spatial imaging (Fig. 1b), and 1D temporal reconstruction (Fig. 1c). Specifically, 2D spatial imaging involves the use of a basis of modulation patterns changing in both transverse directions x and y (for instance, a Hadamard basis) for full 2D image reconstruction. Instead, 1D spatial imaging involves the use of modulation patterns changing only along one direction (such as a properly chosen Fourier basis) coupled to temporal multiplexing of the electron beam on the detector, which should enable a simpler and faster 1D image reconstruction.

The third scenario of temporal reconstruction is conceptually novel. Importantly, the 1D single-pixel reconstruction algorithm works for any dependent variable of the system phase space. This implies that, by choosing a well-defined basis of temporally-changing modulation functions, such as a series of monochromatic periodic harmonics, it would be possible to reconstruct the time dynamics of a sample. The nature of the method would also allow us to reconstruct the dynamical evolution on a temporal scale much smaller than the electron pulse duration because the resolution depends only on the different frequency components of the basis and not on the length of the electron wavepacket. In principle, it could be even be implemented with a continuous electron beam.

Before proceeding to a more detailed description of Electron Single-Pixel Imaging (ESPI), it is instructive to compare the performances of current imaging methods with the potential represented by the ESPI technique. In Fig. 1d, we plot the number of electrons per unit area and unit time – which is a quantity that directly affects sample damage – as a function of the image acquisition time. In general, a larger electron density illuminating the sample would correspond to a faster image acquisition when maintaining a constant signal-to-noise ratio. The electron dose, D , which is defined as the number of electrons per unit area ($e/\text{\AA}^2$), can be obtained as the electron dose per unit time, D_t , multiplied by the exposure time, σ , so we have $D = D_t\sigma$. The number of electrons arriving at the sample is thus given by $N_e = D_t\sigma\delta^2$, where δ^2 is the illuminated area.

Assuming a Poissonian distribution of electron arrivals, the signal-to-noise ratio can be calculated as $\text{SNR} = \sqrt{N_e}$. We can thus rewrite the electron dose per unit time as $D_t = \text{SNR}^2 / (\sigma \delta^2)$. This corresponds to the situation of standard electron imaging, which shows an inverse proportionality between D_t and σ at a constant SNR. In contrast, in ESPI the signal-to-noise ratio scales as the ratio between the number of patterns, M , and the number of pixels, N_{pix} , so we have $\text{SNR}_{\text{SPI}} = \text{SNR}(M/N_{\text{pix}})$. The ESPI electron dose per unit time would then scale as $D_{t,\text{SPI}} = D_t (M/N_{\text{pix}})^2$. Considering that the ensemble of M patterns is generally smaller than the number of pixels N_{pix} , the ESPI dose, $D_{t,\text{SPI}}$, becomes considerably smaller than the dose in standard TEM mode, D_t . The advantage provided by the ESPI method endorses us with the ability to shift the dose curve towards smaller electron densities and faster acquisition times. This analysis remains valid also when comparing the *standard* ultrafast-TEM technique based on stroboscopic acquisition – which usually requires very long exposure times – with the 1D temporal single-pixel reconstruction.

Principles of Single-Pixel Imaging

Single-pixel imaging relies on pre-shaped illumination intensity patterns $H^m(\mathbf{R}_S)$ that are transmitted through a sample described by a spatially-dependent amplitude transmission function $T(\mathbf{R}_S)$ –defining the sample image–, such that the intensity collected at the detector associated with the m^{th} illumination pattern is

$$\chi^m = \int d^2 \mathbf{R}_S T(\mathbf{R}_S) H^m(\mathbf{R}_S), \quad (1)$$

where we integrate over the sample plane and χ^m are the elements of the measurement vector. The target is to reconstruct the sample transmission function

$$T(\mathbf{R}_S) = \sum_m t^m H^m(\mathbf{R}_S) \quad (2)$$

in terms of coefficients t^m . Now we assume that the illumination patterns in general yield

$$\int d^2 \mathbf{R}_S H^m(\mathbf{R}_S) H^{m'}(\mathbf{R}_S) = S^{mm'}, \quad (3)$$

where $S^{mm'}$ are real-valued coefficients. Now, by substituting Eq. (2) in Eq. (1), we retrieve

$$\int d^2 \mathbf{R}_S \sum_m t^m H^m(\mathbf{R}_S) H^{m'}(\mathbf{R}_S) = \chi^{m'}. \quad (4)$$

Notice that if the illumination patterns form an orthonormal basis, we immediately recover $t^m = \chi^m$ (i.e., the intensities recorded at the detector can directly serve as the expansion coefficients). However, in the general case, where Eq. (3) holds, the expansion coefficients are

$$t^m = \sum_{m'} \chi^{m'} (S^{-1})^{mm'}. \quad (5)$$

By substituting the coefficients back in Eq. (2), we find the general formula

$$T(\mathbf{R}_S) = \sum_m \sum_{m'} \chi^{m'} (S^{-1})^{mm'} H^m(\mathbf{R}_S) \quad (6)$$

for the reconstruction of the sample transmission function. It is worth noting that, besides our current choice, a number of different orthogonalization algorithms have been implemented in the literature (see for instance Ref. [29]), which can also be used in combination with our ESPI scheme.

Single-pixel Imaging in a TEM via a Photonic Electron Modulator

We now proceed to analytically describe the scheme utilized to implement the SPI method in an electron microscope. This is shown in Fig. 2, where the sample illumination is performed using structured electron beams created via light-induced manipulation. Efficient and versatile phase and intensity modulation of a free electron can be achieved using a PELM device. In our configuration, the spatial pattern imprinted on the incident light field by a programmable SLM is transferred on the transverse profile of the electron wavepacket by electron-light interaction. This is generally dubbed as the Photon-Induced Near-Field Electron Microscopy (PINEM) effect [11,12,30], although in our configuration we actually exploit the breaking of translational symmetry induced by a thin film (inverse transition radiation) – as described in detail in Ref. [17,31,32] – rather than a confined near field induced by a nanoscale structure. The shaped electron wavepacket is then propagated through the TEM column towards the sample.

The electron-light interaction under consideration admits a simple theoretical description [17,21]: starting with an electron wave function ψ_0 incident on the PELM, after interaction with the light field, the electron wave function is inelastically scattered into quantized components of amplitude

$$\begin{aligned}\psi_\ell^m(\mathbf{R}_{PELM}) &= \psi_0(\mathbf{R}_{PELM}) J_\ell(2|\beta^m(\mathbf{R}_{PELM})|) \exp(i\ell \arg\{-\beta^m(\mathbf{R}_{PELM})\}) \\ &= \psi_0(\mathbf{R}_{PELM}) \mathcal{F}\{\beta^m(\mathbf{R}_{PELM})\},\end{aligned}\quad (7)$$

corresponding to electrons that have gained ($\ell > 0$) or lost ($\ell < 0$) ℓ quanta of photon energy $\hbar\omega$. Here, $\mathcal{F}\{\dots\}$ represents the PINEM operator, which depends on the imprinted variation of the transverse profile, governed by the coupling coefficient

$$\beta^m(\mathbf{R}) = \frac{e}{\hbar\omega} \int dz E_z^m(\mathbf{R}) \exp(-i\omega z/v), \quad (8)$$

where \hbar is the reduced Planck constant, e is the elementary charge, and the light illumination is further characterized by the electric field \mathbf{E}^m (see Supplementary Information for a detailed calculation of β^m in a metallic thin film). We assume that beam electrons have velocity $\mathbf{v} \parallel \hat{z}$. Due to the inelastic nature of the PINEM interaction, post-interaction electrons gain or lose different numbers of quanta, associated with kinetic energy changes $\ell\hbar\omega$. In addition, the corresponding contributions to the wave function in Eq. (7) have different spatial distributions of amplitude and phase. For our purpose, it would be beneficial to place a simple energy filter after the PELM, selecting, for example, the $\ell = 1$ component only (i.e., electrons gaining one photon energy quantum).

A practical approach towards the design of the structured beam sample illumination is to define a suitable ψ_ℓ^m and thus also β^m , study the propagation of the wave function to the sample plane, and then find optimal settings for the aperture size, beam energy, and focal distance in such a way that $H^m(\mathbf{R}_S)$ mimics the optical illumination pattern. For ESPI, we thus impose the inelastically scattered electron wave function, ψ_ℓ^m , to be equal to the target pattern, ψ_T , defined within the chosen basis ($\psi_\ell^m = \psi_T$). Once this is defined, we can retrieve the coupling coefficient, β^m , and, therefore, the light field, E_z^m , to be implemented on the SLM by applying an inverse PINEM transformation, $\mathcal{F}^{-1}\{\dots\}$, to the target pattern ψ_T (see Fig. 2 and also Supplementary Fig. S1 for a Hadamard basis, and Supplementary Fig. S2 for a Fourier basis).

Particularly important is to demonstrate the feasibility of the method also under realistic, non-ideal conditions. We do this by applying a momentum cutoff (ω_0/nc , where $n = 1, 2, 3$) on the retrieved

light field defined by a momentum-dependent point spread function (PSF) to take into account the finite illumination wavelength and range of angles. This produces the actual light field, $E_z^m|_{\text{actual}}$, from which we can calculate the actual coupling coefficient, $\beta^m|_{\text{actual}}$. By applying the PINEM transformation, $\mathcal{F}\{\dots\}$, we can in turn find the actual target pattern, $\psi_T|_{\text{actual}}$.

The sequence of operations is defined in Eq. (9) below and visually shown in Figures 2, S1, and S2:

$$\psi_\ell^m = \psi_T \rightarrow \beta^m = \mathcal{F}^{-1}\{\psi_T\} \rightarrow \beta^m|_{\text{actual}} = \beta^m * \text{PSF}_n \rightarrow \psi_T|_{\text{actual}} = \mathcal{F}\{\beta^m|_{\text{actual}}\}. \quad (9)$$

In order to maximize the efficiency of the electron amplitude and phase modulation, it is beneficial to place the PELM onto a plane along the microscope column where the beam is extended to diameters much larger than the wavelength of the optical illumination. In such a scenario, we can achieve the desired detail in the variation of the transverse wave function profile. However, we then have to rely on electron lenses to focus the beam on the sample.

The focusing action together with the free propagation of the electron wave function between the PELM and the sample planes is described, within the paraxial approximation, as [21]

$$\begin{aligned} \psi_S^m(\mathbf{R}_S, z_S) &\approx \frac{-i\xi}{2\pi} \exp[iq_0(z_S - z_{\text{PELM}})] \cdot \\ &\cdot \exp(-i\xi R_S^2/2) \int d^2\mathbf{R}_{\text{PELM}} \psi_T|_{\text{actual}}(\mathbf{R}_{\text{PELM}}) P(\mathbf{R}_{\text{PELM}}) \cdot \\ &\cdot \exp\left[iq_0 R_{\text{PELM}}^2/2 \left(\frac{1}{z_S - z_{\text{PELM}}} - \frac{1}{f}\right)\right] \exp[-i\xi(x_{\text{PELM}}x_S + y_{\text{PELM}}y_S)], \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

where we have defined $\xi = q_0/(z_S - z_{\text{PELM}})$ with q_0 the electron wave vector that varies with acceleration voltage, and the coordinates $\mathbf{R}_S = (x_S, y_S)$ evolving in the sample $z = z_S$ plane. In addition, $P(\mathbf{R}_{\text{PELM}})$ is a transmission (pupil) function, which becomes 1 if the electron beam passes through an effective aperture placed in the PELM plane and 0 otherwise. We have also replaced the focusing action of all subsequent lenses by a single aberration-free thin lens with a focal distance f placed virtually just after the PELM. The illumination intensity at the sample resulting from Eq. (10) is

$$\begin{aligned} I^m(\mathbf{R}_S) &= |\psi_S^m(\mathbf{R}_S, z_S)|^2 \propto \frac{\xi^2}{4\pi^2} \left| \int d^2\mathbf{R}_{\text{PELM}} J_1(2|\beta^m(\mathbf{R}_{\text{PELM}})|) \exp(i \arg\{-\beta^m(\mathbf{R}_{\text{PELM}})\}) \right. \\ &\times \left. \exp\left[iq_0 R_{\text{PELM}}^2/2 \left(\frac{1}{z_S - z_{\text{PELM}}} - \frac{1}{f}\right)\right] \exp[-i\xi(x_{\text{PELM}}x_S + y_{\text{PELM}}y_S)] \right|^2. \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

In Fig. 2b and Supplementary Figs. S1 and S2, we show the realistic sample patterns obtained for a Hadamard pattern and a Fourier pattern, chosen as examples when using the following parameters: 200 keV electrons, lens focal distance $f = 1$ mm, $z_{\text{PELM}} = 0$, $z_S = 1.008$ mm (defocus of $0.8 \mu\text{m}$), and PELM area of $10 \times 10 \mu\text{m}^2$.

The most efficient reconstruction can be achieved with a binary illumination using the Hadamard basis, where N sample pixels (e.g., discrete \mathbf{R}_S points) can be reconstructed with N patterns [33]. However, because the Hadamard basis adopts +1 and -1 values to ensure orthogonality, in our

case non-orthonormality issues might arise from the fact that we are working with intensity patterns that are never negative. This aspect, together with the imperfect illumination under realistic, non-ideal conditions (see Fig. 2), implies that the actual sample patterns no longer represent an orthonormal basis, and therefore, the reconstructed sample transmission function, $T(\mathbf{R}_S)$, has to be corrected as described in Eqs. (5) and (6) via the overlap matrix $S^{mm'}$. The latter and its inverse are shown in Supplementary Fig. S3 for the Hadamard basis.

Another option for a basis is to use Fourier-like intensity patterns (Fourier basis), which are defined as

$$H(\mathbf{R}_S, \mathbf{K}, \varphi) = a + b \cos(\mathbf{K} \cdot \mathbf{R}_S + \varphi), \quad (12)$$

where \mathbf{K} are spatial frequencies, a and b are constants, and φ is a phase. When using a Fourier basis, the reconstruction is often performed with a three-step (or alternatively four-step) algorithm [33], where we define

$$\Delta_\varphi(\mathbf{K}) = \int d^2\mathbf{R}_S T(\mathbf{R}_S) H(\mathbf{R}_S, \mathbf{K}, \varphi). \quad (13)$$

Then, we calculate

$$\Delta_{\text{Tot}} = (2\Delta_0 - \Delta_{2\pi/3} - \Delta_{4\pi/3}) + i\sqrt{3}(\Delta_{2\pi/3} - \Delta_{4\pi/3}) \quad (14)$$

and finally perform the inverse Fourier transform to reconstruct the sample transmission function

$$T(\mathbf{R}_S) = \text{FT}^{-1}\{\Delta_{\text{Tot}}(\mathbf{K})\}, \quad (15)$$

which can be done after collecting the intensities at the detector obtained with varying spatial frequencies.

Image reconstruction using Hadamard and Fourier bases

We show next several examples of image reconstruction using different bases. We consider a Siemens star and a ghost image. The former is a binary $\{0,1\}$ image with sharp transitions, whereas the latter presents small features, is asymmetric, and shows a gradual intensity variation from 0 to 1. This allows us to test in full the capabilities of the method.

In Fig. 3a, we plot the ideal and reconstructed Siemens star and ghost image considering different cutoffs for a Hadamard basis. Clearly, the reconstructions reproduce all the main features of the original images, although we also encounter some noise and even a few negative values, which should not appear. The latter is due to ill-conditioned matrix inversion that we need to use for the reconstruction to compensate for the non-orthonormality of the involved patterns. In Fig. 3b, we plot the results of image reconstruction using a Fourier basis. Although for the Siemens-star reconstruction with the Fourier basis is performing similarly as with the Hadamard basis, for the ghost image it is clear that the Fourier basis with the same number of patterns (64×64) yields artifacts: a faint *mirror-reflected* ghost is superimposing on the actual one. The reconstruction with the Fourier basis becomes considerably better when taking into account a phase offset, so that the Fourier pattern would no longer be symmetric with respect to the origin. In Fig. 3c, we have considered an offset of $\varphi = \pi/4$ for the corresponding reconstructed sample images. As a result, the reconstructed ghost image no longer exhibits the faint *mirror-reflected* artifact that was visible in Fig. 3b.

As an additional note, we comment on the comparison between different image reconstruction algorithms (standard vs 4-step Fourier) using the Hadamard and Fourier bases within the ideal scenario of perfect illumination. This is shown in Supplementary Fig. S4 for the Siemens star. The 4-step Fourier algorithm retrieves the phase of the FFT by measuring the gradient of the image [33]. The reconstruction is therefore smoother than when using the standard algorithm. The price to pay is that one needs four times more measurements (i.e., four times the electron dose). As expected, the Hadamard basis performs better. However, with the Hadamard basis one needs to necessarily use all the 4096 patterns in the stack, as otherwise one could introduce artefacts, unless very time-consuming compressive sensing algorithms are used. In this respect, the Fourier basis is more flexible because one can decide the resolution of the final reconstruction prior to performing the experiment.

As a final aspect, we present a possible implementation of the 1D temporal ESPI reconstruction scheme. The basic idea is to be able to reconstruct the dynamic behavior of a sample – for instance, its dielectric response to an optically-induced electronic excitation – using a sequence of temporally-modulated electron pulses with varying periodicity. In Fig. 4, we show the schematics of the experiment, where a sequence of long light pulses with varying periods T_j couple to the electron pulse via inverse transition radiation as mediated by the metallic plate. The longitudinally-modulated electron pulse then interacts with the sample in its excited state and, for each period T_j , a signal I_j is measured. In terms of the single-pixel formalism, this means that we are choosing a one-dimensional Fourier basis, and therefore temporal reconstruction of the full dynamic evolution of the sample can now be obtained via a Fourier-like expansion of the measured signals:

$$I(t) = \sum_j (I_j - \langle I_j \rangle) \left[\cos\left(\frac{2\pi}{T_j} t\right) - \frac{1}{2} \right]. \quad (16)$$

It is important to note that the temporal resolution of the measurement no longer depends on the duration of the electron and light pulses, but only on the frequency bandwidth of the light field used for electron modulation. This aspect is extremely interesting because it opens the possibility of using continuous electron and light beams, provided that an efficient electron-light coupling is achieved [34,35,36,37,38]. A possible technological implementation of such scheme can be realized by using an optical parametric amplifier (OPA) coupled to a difference frequency generator (DFG). Such a configuration would provide light fields with periods in the 0.8 fs – 50 fs range, making our approach invaluable to investigate sample dynamics with a temporal resolution that is far below that of state-of-the-art ultrafast electron microscopy, and equally combined with the atomic spatial resolution provided by electron beams.

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Figure 1. Schematic representation of different single-pixel schemes that are amenable to implementation in a transmission electron microscope for 2D spatial imaging (*panel a*), 1D spatial imaging (*panel b*), and 1D temporal reconstruction (*panel c*). In *panel d*, we show the correlation between electron dose per unit time ($e/\text{\AA}^2/\text{s}$) and acquisition time (s) for different imaging methods (standard TEM and single-pixel imaging). We consider a current of 100 pA illuminating an area of $1 \mu\text{m}^2$, and a ratio M/N_{pix} of 0.1 and 0.01 (when using compressive sensing).

Figure 2. *Panel a:* Schematic representation of the experimental layout considered for the single-pixel imaging method, implemented by using structured electron beams that are in turn created via light-based manipulation. In our configuration, the spatial pattern imprinted on the incident light field by a programmable spatial light modulator is transferred on the transverse profile of the electron wavepacket by electron-light interaction. *Panel b:* Sequence of operations used to calculate the transverse distribution of the electron beam arriving on the sample either when starting from an ideal target pattern or when considering realistic non-ideal conditions. We take a pattern from a Hadamard basis for this example.

Figure 3. Image reconstruction of a Siemens-star and a ghost-image performed using a Hadamard basis (*panel a*), a Fourier basis (*panel b*), and a Fourier basis with a $\pi/4$ phase shift (*panel c*). Reconstructed images are shown for different momentum cutoffs (ω_0/nc , where $n = 1, 2, 3$) on the retrieved light field.

Figure 4. Schematic representation of the 1D temporal single-pixel reconstruction of a sample dynamics. A sequence of long light pulses with varying periods T_j couple to the electron pulse via inverse transition radiation mediated by a metallic plate. We show three different periods: $T_1 < T_2 < T_3$. The longitudinally-modulated electron pulse then interacts with the sample in its excited state and, for each period T_j , a scattered intensity I_j is measured. The full temporal evolution of the sample is finally reconstructed from a Fourier-like transformation of the measured signals (see main text for details).

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- ¹ M. P. Edgar et al., Principles and prospects for single-pixel imaging, *Nat. Photon.* **13**, 13 (2019).
- ² M. F. Duarte et al. Single-pixel imaging via compressive sampling, *IEEE Signal Process. Mag.* **25**, 83–91 (2008).
- ³ M. Gibson, S. D. Johnson, and M. J. Padgett, Single-pixel imaging 12 years on: a review, *Opt. Express* **28**, 28190-28208 (2020)
- ⁴ C. A. Osorio Quero, D. Durini, J. Rangel-Magdaleno, and J. Martinez-Carranza, Single-pixel imaging: An overview of different methods to be used for 3D space reconstruction in harsh environments, *Rev. Sci. Instrum.* **92**, 111501 (2021).
- ⁵ E. J. Candes, J. Romberg, and T. Tao, *IEEE Trans. Inf. Theory* **52**, 489 (2006).
- ⁶ O. Katz, Y. Bromberg, and Y. Silberberg, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **95**, 131110 (2009).
- ⁷ L. Kovarik, A. Stevens, A. Liyu, and N. D. Browning, Implementing an accurate and rapid sparse sampling approach for low-dose atomic resolution STEM imaging, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **109**, 164102 (2016).
- ⁸ Q. Chen, C. Dwyer, G. Sheng, C. Zhu, X. Li, C. Zheng, Y. Zhu, Imaging Beam-Sensitive Materials by Electron Microscopy, *Adv. Mater.* **32**, 1907619 (2020).
- ⁹ R. F. Egerton, Radiation damage to organic and inorganic specimens in the TEM, *Micron* **119**, 72-87 (2019).
- ¹⁰ S. Li, F. Cropp, K. Kabra, T. J. Lane, G. Wetzstein, P. Musumeci, and D. Ratner, Electron Ghost Imaging, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **121**, 114801 (2018)
- ¹¹ B. Barwick and D. J. Flannigan and A. H. Zewail, Photon-induced near-field electron microscopy, *Nature* **462**, 902-906 (2009).
- ¹² A. Feist, K. E. Echternkamp, J. Schauss, S. V. Yalunin, S. Schäfer & C. Ropers, Quantum coherent optical phase modulation in an ultrafast transmission electron microscope, *Nature* **521**, 200–203 (2015).
- ¹³ G. M. Vanacore, I. Madan, F. Carbone, Spatio-temporal shaping of a free-electron wave function via coherent light–electron interaction, *La Rivista del Nuovo Cimento* **43**, 567-597 (2020)
- ¹⁴ K. E. Priebe, C. Rathje, S. V. Yalunin, T. Hohage, A. Feist, S. Schäfer, and C. Ropers, Attosecond electron pulse trains and quantum state reconstruction in ultrafast transmission electron microscopy, *Nat. Photon.* **11**, 793 (2017);
- ¹⁵ M. Kozák, N. Schönenberger, and P. Hommelhoff, Ponderomotive generation and detection of attosecond free-electron pulse trains, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **120**, 103203 (2018);
- ¹⁶ Y. Morimoto and P. Baum, Diffraction and microscopy with attosecond electron pulse trains, *Nat. Phys.* **14**, 252 (2018)

-
- ¹⁷ G. M. Vanacore et al., Attosecond coherent control of free-electron wave functions using semi-infinite light fields, *Nat. Commun.* **9**, 2694 (2018);
- ¹⁸ G. M. Vanacore et al., Ultrafast generation and control of an electron vortex beam via chiral plasmonic near fields, *Nat. Mater.* **18**, 573–579 (2019)
- ¹⁹ I. Madan, G. M. Vanacore, S. Gargiulo, T. LaGrange, F. Carbone, The quantum future of microscopy: Wave function engineering of electrons, ions, and nuclei, *App. Phys. Lett.* **116**, 230502 (2020)
- ²⁰ A. Konečná, F. Iyikanat, F. J. García de Abajo, Entangling free electrons and optical excitations, *arXiv:2202.00604*
- ²¹ A. Konečná and F. J. García de Abajo, Electron beam aberration correction using optical near fields, *Physical Review Letters* **125**, 030801 (2020).
- ²² F. J. García de Abajo and A. Konečná, Optical modulation of electron beams in free space, *Physical Review Letters* **126**, 123901 (2021).
- ²³ T. Sekia, Y. Ikuhara, N. Shibata, Theoretical framework of statistical noise in scanning transmission electron microscopy, *Ultramicroscopy* **193**, 118-125 (2018).
- ²⁴ N. Mevenkamp, P. Binev, W. Dahmen, P. M. Voyles, A. B. Yankovich and B Berkels, Poisson noise removal from high-resolution STEM images based on periodic block matching, *Advanced Structural and Chemical Imaging* **1**, 3 (2015)
- ²⁵ D. Stellinga et al., Time-of-flight 3D imaging through multimode optical fibers, *Science* **374**, 1395-1399 (2021)
- ²⁶ W. Verhoeven, J. F. M. van Rens, W. F. Toonen, et al, Time-of-flight electron energy loss spectroscopy by longitudinal phase space manipulation with microwave cavities, *Struct. Dyn.* **5**, 051101 (2018)
- ²⁷ E. Nogales and S. H. W. Scheres, Cryo-EM: A Unique Tool for the Visualization of Macromolecular Complexity. *Molecular Cell* **58**, 677-689 (2015)
- ²⁸ S. Jonic, C.O.S. Sorzano & N. Boisset, Comparison of single-particle analysis and electron tomography approaches: an overview, *Journal of Microscopy*, **232**, 562–579 (2008).
- ²⁹ A. Kallepalli et al., Ghost imaging with electron microscopy inspired, non-orthogonal phase masks, DOI:10.21203/rs.3.rs-1111193/v1
- ³⁰ L Piazza et al., Simultaneous observation of the quantization and the interference pattern of a plasmonic near-field, *Nat. Commun.* **6**, 6407 (2015)
- ³¹ I. Madan et al., Holographic imaging of electromagnetic fields via electron-light quantum interference, *Sci. Adv.* **5** eaav8358 (2019)
- ³² Y. Morimoto and P. Baum, Attosecond control of electron beams at dielectric and absorbing membranes, *Phys. Rev. A* **97**, 033815 (2018).
- ³³ Z. Zhang, X. Wang, G. Zheng, and J. Zhong, Hadamard single-pixel imaging versus Fourier

single-pixel imaging, *Optics Express* **25**, 19619-19639 (2017).

³⁴ O. Kfir, H. Lourenço-Martins, G. Storeck, M. Sivilis, T. R. Harvey, T. J. Kippenberg, A. Feist & C. Ropers, Controlling free electrons with optical whispering-gallery modes, *Nature* **582**, 46–49 (2020).

³⁵ K. Wang, R. Dahan, M. Shentcis, Y. Kauffmann, A. Ben-Hayun, O. Reinhardt, S. Tsesses, I. Kaminer, Coherent Interaction between Free Electrons and Cavity Photons, *Nature* **582**, 50 (2020).

³⁶ R. Dahan, S. Nehemia, M. Shentcis, O. Reinhardt, Y. Adiv, X. Shi, O. Be'er, M. H. Lynch, Y. Kurman, K. Wang and I. Kaminer, Resonant phase-matching between a light wave and a free-electron wavefunction, *Nature Physics* **16**, 1123-1131 (2020)

³⁷ R. Dahan, A. Gorlach, U. Haeusler, A. Karnieli, O. Eyal, P. Yousefi, M. Segev, A. Arie, G. Eisenstein, P. Hommelhoff, and I. Kaminer, Imprinting the quantum statistics of photons on free electrons, *Science* **373**, 1309-1310, (2021)

³⁸ J.-W. Henke, A. Sajid Raja, A. Feist, G. Huang, G. Arend, Y. Yang, F. J. Kappert, R. Ning Wang, M. Möller, J. Pan, J. Liu, O. Kfir, C. Ropers & T. J. Kippenberg, Integrated photonics enables continuous-beam electron phase modulation, *Nature* **600**, 653–658 (2021)

SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Single-Pixel Imaging in Space and Time with Optically-Modulated Free Electrons

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COUPLING COEFFICIENT BETA FOR A HOMOGENEOUS THIN FILM

The coupling coefficient β [see Eq. (2) in the main text] for a superposition of p -polarized light waves impinging from the $z < 0$ region with angle θ relative to the normal z direction on a self-standing homogeneous thin film of thickness d can be written

$$\beta^m(\mathbf{R}) = \int_{-k_0}^{k_0} dk_x \int_{-k_0}^{k_0} dk_y \exp(i\mathbf{K} \cdot \mathbf{R}) \beta_{\mathbf{K}}^m, \quad (\text{S1})$$

which incorporates the fact that, due to the finite wavelength of light $\lambda = 2\pi/k_0 = 2\pi c/\omega$, we can imprint patterns with a precision limited by diffraction (i.e., the integral over transverse light wave vectors $\mathbf{K} = (k_x, k_y)$ is limited to the range $K < k_0$). The contributions of the different transverse wave vector components are

$$\beta_{\mathbf{K}}^m = \frac{ieK}{\hbar\omega k_0} \alpha_{\mathbf{K}} \left[\frac{1}{\omega/v - k_z} + \frac{r_p}{\omega/v + k_z} - \frac{t_p \exp(-i\omega d/v)}{\omega/v - k_z} + A \frac{\exp[i(-\omega/v + k'_z)d] - 1}{\omega/v - k'_z} + B \frac{\exp[-i(\omega/v + k'_z)d] - 1}{\omega/v + k'_z} \right]. \quad (\text{S2})$$

Here, the coefficients $\alpha_{\mathbf{K}}$ are controlled through the proper settings of the spatial light modulator, and r_p , t_p , A , and B are given by

$$r_p = r_p^0 \left[1 - \frac{(t_p^0)^2 (k'_z/k_z) \exp(2ik'_z d)}{1 - (r_p^0)^2 \exp(2ik'_z d)} \right], \quad (\text{S3})$$

$$t_p = \frac{(t_p^0)^2 (k'_z/k_z) \exp(ik'_z d)}{1 - (r_p^0)^2 \exp(2ik'_z d)}, \quad (\text{S4})$$

$$A = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\epsilon}} \frac{t_p^0}{1 - (r_p^0)^2 \exp(2ik'_z d)}, \quad (\text{S5})$$

$$B = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\epsilon}} \frac{-t_p^0 r_p^0 \exp(2ik'_z d)}{1 - (r_p^0)^2 \exp(2ik'_z d)}, \quad (\text{S6})$$

where r_p^0 and t_p^0 are the Fresnel reflection coefficients expressed in terms of the permittivity of the film material ϵ as

$$r_p^0 = \frac{\epsilon k_z - k'_z}{\epsilon k_z + k'_z}, \quad (\text{S7})$$

$$t_p^0 = \frac{2\sqrt{\epsilon} k_z}{\epsilon k_z + k'_z}, \quad (\text{S8})$$

with out-of-plane light wave vector components k_z and k'_z given by

$$k_z = \sqrt{k_0^2 - K^2}, \quad (\text{S9})$$

$$k'_z = k_0 \sqrt{\epsilon - K^2/k_0^2}. \quad (\text{S10})$$

In the perfect-electric-conductor (PEC) limit for the film material, we have $r_p = r_p^0 = 1$ and $t_p = 0$, so the \mathbf{K} -dependent amplitudes of the coupling coefficient reduce to

$$\beta_{\mathbf{K},\text{PEC}}^m = \frac{2ieK}{\hbar k_0 v} \frac{\alpha_{\mathbf{K}}}{(\omega/v)^2 - (k_z)^2}. \quad (\text{S11})$$

Figure S1. Sequence of operations used to calculate the transverse distribution of beam electrons arriving on the sample when starting from an ideal target pattern and considering realistic non-ideal conditions. Here, we plot results for a pattern taken from a Hadamard basis.

Figure S2. Sequence of operations used to calculate the transverse distribution of beam electrons arriving on the sample when starting from an ideal target pattern and considering realistic non-ideal conditions. Here, we plot results for a pattern taken from a Fourier basis.

Figure S3. Overlap matrix calculated for the Hadamard basis when considering imperfect illumination of the sample plotted for the three different cutoffs considered in this work.

Reconstructed images with perfect illumination

Figure S4. Effect of both different image reconstruction algorithms (standard vs 4-steps with a Fourier basis) and different bases (Hadamard and Fourier) on the quality of the reconstructed image. For the Fourier basis with standard reconstruction, the observed super-periodicity originates from the phase alignment of all the patterns. It can be removed by using a random phase.